

Photophysical investigations on interaction of *p*-bromoacetanilide with eosin in solution

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Abstract : The photophysical properties of *p*-bromoacetanilide were studied in neat methanol solution. The characteristic excitation and emission spectra were recorded and compared with the behavior in the solid state. Interaction of *p*-bromoacetanilide with an anionic fluorophore, eosin, was studied by steady state measurements and the behavior was gauged by using Stern-Volmer kinetics. A significant decrease in fluorescence intensity was observed and this was attributed to a combined phenomenon of static and dynamic quenching. The ground state interaction between the halide ions were found to be predominant than the dynamic quenching. The rate constants of the quenching phenomena were obtained from modified Stern-Volmer equation.

Keywords : *p*-Bromoacetanilide, eosin, methanol, luminescence, quencher.

Introduction

Photophysics of organic molecules has been the field of interest to understand their excited state properties. It helps in exploring various phenomena taking place in the systems (solid and liquid). This study may help not only in designing new molecules but also to explore the possibilities of various applications. Some of these applications include laser dyes, probes for polymers and biological systems, chemical sensors, molecular switches etc.^{1,2}. Such studies involve the intricate analysis of the luminescence properties of these molecules both in the ground and excited states. Eosin, an anionic surfactant dye is well known for its luminescent property. It belongs to the family of Xanthenes, which is already established for its high molar extinction coefficients and fluorescence quantum yields and is also used in FRET studies as potent acceptors³. Detailed investigations regarding the influence of eosin on the absorption and fluorescence behaviors of various fluorophores have been already reported and in particular, eosin, as a quencher has been well explored⁴.

Quenching of fluorescence has become an interesting field of study in recent times. The availability of heavy atoms playing a key role in an efficient quenching phenomenon was first identified by Francis Perrin as early as in 1926 and subsequently cited frequently in recent times⁵. Heavy atom quenching may occur in two modes, viz. internal and external, wherein, the heavy atom may be a part of the chromophore itself as in the former^{6,7}, or may be a discrete identity like external ions or molecules^{8,9} as in the latter, respectively. However, the external process requires a closer contact between the fluorophore and the quencher, usually, in the form of a statistical charge transfer complex in the excited state¹⁰. The mechanism of quenching may also differ with respect to the nature of molecules in interaction, viz. static and dynamic, studied by following the steady state fluorescence and lifetime profiles of the probe in presence of the quencher^{11,12}.

Previous studies on heavy atom quenching reveals bromine playing a key role, both as an intra- and inter-molecular quencher¹³. Here, in our current investigation,

we have studied the photophysical behavior of brominated acetanilide in the presence of eosin in an alcoholic medium. The focus is on the influence of bromine atoms of eosin on the steady state emission of *p*-bromoacetanilide (pBA) which is known so far only for its pharmaceutical applications. pBA as an analgesic drug when it is metabolized in the body and is also used as a precursor for various medicinal applications. The molecular structure of pBA (Scheme 1) involves an aromatic moiety with the N-H, C=O functional groups.

Scheme 1. Structure of (a) *p*-bromoacetanilide (pBA) and (b) eosin.

Materials and methods :

p-Bromoacetanilide and eosin were obtained from S.D. Fine chemicals Pvt. Ltd. and were used as received. Methanol used was of HPLC grade and was obtained from Qualigens India Ltd. Absorption spectra were recorded in an Agilent 8453 diode array spectrophotometer. Fluorescence spectra were recorded using a Horiba Jobin Yuonfluoromax 4B spectrofluorimeter.

Results and discussion

The structures of pBA and eosin are as shown in Scheme 1.

The absorption, excitation and emission spectra of pBA recorded in methanol are depicted in Fig. 1. It was interesting to note that the absorption spectrum of pBA showed absorption peaks only in the UV region, but when excita-

Fig. 1. (a) Absorption spectrum, (b) excitation spectrum and (c) emission spectrum of *p*-bromoacetanilide ($\lambda_{exc} = 450$ nm).

tion spectrum was scanned from 200 to 700 nm, it showed a clear peak at 363 nm. This peak is attributed to the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition that occurs from the carbonyl group to the amino group present in the acetanilide moiety. However, reports are available for the masking of this absorption band in the visible region for the parent acetanilide molecule itself even at high concentrations (3×10^{-3} mol/L)¹⁴. When excited at λ_{max} (363 nm), it showed a characteristic emission at 440 nm. These recordings were compared with the absorption and emission characteristics of pBA when recorded as a crystal¹⁵. Similar observations were made in the solid state; a maximum reduc-

tion in transmittance was observed around 360 nm. This evidences the stability of the probe in the ground state as a free molecule both in solid and liquid media.

As the probe (pBA) is found to be favourably emissive in the visible region, in the present study, we set to analyse the photophysical properties of pBA. We have studied the interaction of this molecule with that of an anionic fluorophore, eosin, by following their steady state absorption and emission characteristics. The photophysical behavior of free eosin is as shown in Fig. 2. The dye absorbs maximum at 523 nm and when excited at 450 nm emits at 548 nm. However, the absorbance of this fluorophore is negligible at the region of absorption of our probe (pBA). Hence, it is probable that the fluorophore does not interfere with the luminescence of pBA and for this reason, the usage of this molecule in the current study is justified.

Fig. 2. (a) Absorption spectrum and (b) emission spectrum of eosin ($\lambda_{exc} = 450$ nm).

The absorption spectra of pBA (1×10^{-5} M) with increasing concentrations of eosin (0 to 3.5×10^{-6} M) are as shown in the Fig. 3. The figure reveals that, at the excitation wavelength of 363 nm, no significant change in absorbance of pBA was observed with increasing concentrations of eosin. Hence, the steady state emission of pBA with successive additions of eosin was recorded by exciting the samples at 363 nm. The emission spectrum is shown in Fig. 4 which shows a substantial decrease in intensity and there was also no significant spectral shift observed at the emission maximum of pBA. Such a decrease in fluorescence intensity, usually referred to as

Fig. 3. Absorption spectrum of *p*-bromoacetanilide with successive additions of eosin : (a) 0, (b) 0.5×10^{-6} M, (c) 1×10^{-6} M, (d) 1.5×10^{-6} M, (e) 2×10^{-6} M, (f) 2.5×10^{-6} M, (g) 3×10^{-6} M, (h) 3.5×10^{-6} M.

Fig. 4. Emission spectrum of *p*-bromoacetanilide with successive additions of eosin : (a) 0, (b) 0.5×10^{-6} M, (c) 1×10^{-6} M, (d) 1.5×10^{-6} M, (e) 2×10^{-6} M, (f) 2.5×10^{-6} M, (g) 3×10^{-6} M, (h) 3.5×10^{-6} M, (i) 4×10^{-6} M, (j) 4.5×10^{-6} M.

quenching may be due to many reasons like collisional deactivation, energy transfer, electron transfer or may also be due to complex formations in the ground state. Nevertheless, the modes of quenching can be easily differentiated from one another by calculating the rate constants, finding out the distances between the fluorophore and the probe etc.

Analysis of reaction mechanisms by constructing the Stern-Volmer plots provides a great deal in deciding the mode of energy decay. A plot of F_0/F or τ_0/τ vs $[Q]$, where F_0 , F and τ_0 , τ are the fluorescence intensities and lifetimes of the probe in the absence and presence of quencher $[Q]$ respectively, provides a straight line with an intercept value of 1 in case of a bimolecular quenching phenomenon¹⁶.

With the fluorescence intensities of pBA in the presence of various concentrations of eosin, we constructed the Stern-Volmer plot which is as shown in Fig. 5. It was interesting to observe that the plot showed an upward curvature which is a clear indication of the fact that the

Fig. 5. Stern-Volmer plot of intensities of pBA in presence of eosin.

mode of energy decay was both due to static and dynamic quenching. Since, for an usual static or a dynamic quenching phenomenon, the Stern-Volmer plot happens to be a linear one. Whereas, in our investigation, it was not found to be a linear one rather it was a curvature. This is due to the fact that, a combined quenching process has taken place between the probe and the quencher and hence the plot is governed by eq. (1), as

$$\frac{F_0}{F} = (1 + k_q \tau_0 [Q]) (1 + k_a [Q]) \quad (1)$$

where, k_q is the bimolecular quenching rate constant which is proportional to the sum of the diffusion co-efficients of the probe and the quencher (pBA and eosin in our case) which happens during a pure dynamic quenching process and k_a , is the association constant which involves a complex formation between the probe and the fluorophore, a case of pure static quenching. Hence, as inferred, values of k_q and k_a could be evaluated numerically only in case of a pure dynamic or a static quenching phenomena. However, the strategic reasoning of the combined quenching observed in our case was successfully evaluated as follows.

In case of unavailability of fluorescence lifetime measurements, the equation can be modified as

$$\frac{F_0}{F} = (1 + k_{APP} [Q]) \quad (2)$$

where k_{APP} is the apparent quenching constant and is calculated for each quencher concentration¹⁶ as,

$$k_{APP} = \left(\frac{F_0}{F} - 1 \right) \frac{1}{[Q]} = (k_q + k_a) + k_q k_a [Q] \quad (3)$$

Hence, the modified Stern-Volmer relation was analysed by plotting k_{APP} vs $[Q]$ which is presented in Fig. 6. It was found that the apparent quenching constant was in the range of $10^5 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ which is due to a combined

Fig. 6. Modified Stern-Volmer plot of apparent rate constants in presence of eosin.

static and dynamic quenching phenomenon. From the values of the intercept ($k_q + k_a$) and gradient ($k_q \cdot k_a$) of the plot obtained, the individual rate constants were calculated as $k_q = 7.72 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k_a = 2.32 \times 10^4$

$M^{-1} s^{-1}$. As inferred from the rate constants, the ground state complex formation is found to play a major role in intensity quenching when compared to the excited state dynamic quenching. The reason cited is the effective Van der Waals interaction between the halide ions of the probe (pBA) and the quencher (eosin) in the ground state itself. Such a non-fluorescent complex formed in the ground state effectively quenches the fluorescence intensity of the probe. The uncomplexed probe is further quenched in the excited state by the eosin molecules by a dynamic pathway which is quantified by the dynamic quenching constant.

Conclusion

A photophysical investigation of the interaction between the well known drug *p*-bromoacetanilide and an anionic surfactant dye eosin was carried out. The spectroscopic behavior of pBA drug in the methanolic medium was found to be very similar to that observed in the crystal form. The steady state observations indicated an effective quenching of the fluorescence intensity of pBA in presence of eosin. The mechanism of quenching was analysed using Stern-Volmer kinetics, and a combined quenching was identified as the mode of energy decay. Hence, using a modified Stern-Volmer relation, the individual values of association and quenching constants were calculated numerically. The halide-halide interaction between the probe and the quencher was found to dominate the quenching process.

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